

Relationship between Child Abuse and Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students in Southern Kaduna Senatorial District, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study examined relationship between Child Abuse, Self-Esteem and Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students in Southern Kaduna Senatorial District, Kaduna State. Four research questions guided the conduct of the study and four hypotheses were tested. Correlational research design was used for this study. The population for the study comprised 3,621 JSSII students and the sample of 351 respondents was used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection, a structured questionnaire named Child Abuse and Self-esteem of Students Questionnaire (CASESQ) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT). Mean and Standard Deviation was used to analyze the four research questions while inferential statistics of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between physical abuse, sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary student in southern senatorial district Kaduna state. Based on the findings, the study recommended amongst others that Government and non-Governmental organizations should liaise to ensure that child abuse through physical means is prohibited and discouraged. Enact law prohibiting child physical abuse of children and ensure that offenders are prosecuted. This will enhance learning achievement in schools.

Keywords: Physical Abuse, Sexual Abuse and Academic Achievement

Introduction

Education is regarded as the catalyst for development as well as a process for bringing positive change in the society. The invaluable roles and contributions of education in the development of an individual and the society cannot be over emphasized. This implies that children are the leaders of tomorrow therefore, anything that affects them at home will definitely affect their level of academic achievement. Academic achievement refers to how well a student is accomplishing his or her task and studies. Academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university. Academic achievement should be considered to be a multifaceted construct that comprises different domains of learning. Because the field of academic achievement is very wide-ranging and covers a broad variety of educational outcomes, the definition of academic achievement depends on the indicators used to measure it. Among the many criteria that indicate academic achievement, there are very general indicators such as procedural and declarative knowledge acquired in an educational system, more curricular-based criteria such as grades or performance on an educational achievement test, and cumulative indicators of academic achievement such as educational degrees and certificates. Tenina (2013), observed that all criteria have one thing in common that they represent intellectual endeavors and thus, more or less, mirror the intellectual capacity of a person. In developed societies, academic achievement plays an important role in every person's life. Academic achievement as measured by the GPA (grade point average) or by standardized assessments designed for selection purpose such as the SAT (Scholastic Assessment Test) determines whether a student will have the opportunity to continue his or her education (e.g., to attend a university). Therefore, academic achievement defines whether one can take part in higher education, and based on the educational degrees one attains, influences one's vocational career after education. Besides the relevance for an individual, academic achievement is of utmost importance for the wealth of a nation and its prosperity (Kaplan & Saccuzzo, 2014).

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This study will provide information about different indicators of a students' academic achievement; such information will be used to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of a student academic achievement and to guide educational policy decisions. Given the individual and societal importance of academic achievement, it is not surprising that academic achievement is the research focus of many scientists; for example, in psychology or educational disciplines, the article focuses on the explanation, determination, enhancement, and assessment of academic achievement as investigated by educational psychologists. The history of child abuse is as old as humanity. It persists from century to century with different outlooks and in severity. Child abuse is any physical or mental injury, mistreatment, neglect, beating, and sexual molestation of a child by a parent, guardian, someone or the public (Nweze & Owo, 2014). Child abuse is becoming a universal phenomenal in the current world societies despite the fact the child's right have been recognized even to some extent, protected by legislation and constitutions in many countries of the world. Child abuse may probably have some major economic implications for Nigeria schools and their students. In Nigeria cases of child abuse is as common as the air we breathe in, this is in view of the fact that there can hardly be a day without news report about child abuse. Many of these cases of child abuse went unreported. Child abuse has been defined by the African network for the prevention and protection against child abuse and neglect (ANPPCAN) as the intentional and unintentional acts which endanger the physical health, emotional, moral and the educational welfare of the child. Augustine and Abubakar (2016), opined that there is no safe place for children anymore because child abuse is rampant everywhere. There are three major categories of child abuse: physical abuse, psychological or emotional abuse and verbal abuse (Peter & Anake, 2015).

Child abuse has become an apparent endless vicious cycle that hurts the image of the country and the dignity of those involved. Child abuse can occur in a child's home or in the originations, school, or communities the child interacts with. There are several categories of child abuse: neglect, physical abuse, psychological or emotional child maltreatment, children used In rituals, battering, early marriage, child soldering, child prostitution, children used in hawking, human trafficking, child abandonment, any act and series of acts of commission by a parent or other caregiver that results in harm or threat of harm to a child (Leeb et al., 2018). The researcher opined that child abuse is any act which result in death, serious physical or emotional harm, sexual abuse and exploitation, an act and failure to act which present an immerse risk of serious harm, therefore, child abuse is caused by poverty and lack of parental care, other factors include unemployment, conflicts and polygamous homes. Denga (2012), opined that child abuse is exposing children to painful and unwanted suffering knowingly or unknowingly.

According to Nweze and Owo (2014), child abuse has emerged as one of the serious social problems that need the attention of everyone due to the fact that it may have devastating effects on the academic achievement of students. Child abuse is still a hidden subject in Nigeria because most people who witness it simply ignore it. Child abuse sometimes leads to low self-esteem and self-interest in most of the students in southern senatorial district of Kaduna state which in turn encourages them to engage in a variety of self-destructive behaviors that affects their academic achievement as stated in the junior WAEC result of 2017 where 75% passed and 25% failed, while in 2018 46% passed and 54% failed, and in2019, 42% passed and 58% failed English Language, as reported by Zonal office Kafanchan in 2021.

Physical abuse is one of the most common forms of child maltreatment. Physical abuse is the injury inflicted upon a person with cruel and/or malicious intent. Physical abuse can be punching, kicking, biting, burning, or harming a person physically. According to World Health Organization 2019, Physical abuse is an action or inaction which result in actual or potential physical harm, that are within the control of or preventable by parents, care givers, or authorized persons (such as school teachers). physical abuse is any intentional act causing injury or trauma to another person by way of bodily contact. In most cases, children are the victims as in cases of domestic violence, physical violence and physical assault. Physical abuse is intentional bodily injury like slapping, kicking, pinching, choking, shoving, or inappropriately using drugs or physical restraints on an individual. Physical abuse according to Elarousy and Shaqiqi (2017) is the intentional use of physical force against a person that can lead to harm for the individual's health, survival and development. Physical abuse can be anything that causes pain to any part of the body like slapping, hitting or kicking. Physical abuse can be in a form of domestic violence or family violence. Physical abuse is when a parent, a primary caregiver, or any other person who has responsibility for the person through an action like beating or stabbing, causes injury, death, emotional harm, or risk of serious harm to an individual (Altafim & Linhares, 2016).

Sexual abuse is passive in every part of the world. The problem of sexual abuse has received the attention of scholars from a variety of life domains. (Menon et al, 2011). Its consequences are devastating as sexually abused victims may show many internalized and externalized behavioral, emotional and cognitive problems during childhood and adulthood. Sexual abuse has been defined as the involvement of a person in sexual activity that he or she does not fully comprehend and is unable to give informed consent to and for which the person is not developmentally prepared. According to Murray (2014), sexual

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abuse towards children and adolescents is a stark reality worldwide. Most children and families do not report cases of abuse and exploitation probably because of stigma, fear and lack of trust in the authorities. The National Demographic Health Survey (NDHS) report in 2008 suggest that over 25% of adolescents in Nigeria often experience the first sexual abuse at the age of 15 years. However, cases reported are less than unreported cases by parents and guidance of the victim. A common misconception about sexual abuse is that it is a rare event against girls by male in poor inner-city areas. Sexual abuse is a global phenomenon that may occur across cultures and socio-economic groups might have profound long term negative consequences.

That a child needs academic achievement to succeed in life is a fact that is unquestionable. Despite the increase in effort by both the Nigerian government and Kaduna State in particular towards improving the quality of learning in the State secondary school education, poor academic achievement persists especially in English language within the southern senatorial district of the state. The incessant poor performance of student at the junior WAEC examination in English Language is worrisome. In 2017, 75% passed while 25% failed, in 2018, 46% passed and 54% failed, in 2019, 42% passed and 58% failed report by Zonal office kafanchan. This became a source of concern to the researcher. Academic achievement liberates people from the shackles of illiteracy and make one a better citizen in the society. Humans continue to acquire knowledge right from childhood till death. It is a fact that human gives birth to baby with empty brain that is no form of knowledge in the brain during child birth which is what psychologist called *Tabula Rasa*. As human grow in life they continue to acquire knowledge right from childhood. This happens to be a period in life where the human brain is much active to receive knowledge. Physically abused children seem to perform worst in school compared with non-abused peers. The researcher observed that children that are subject to physical and sexual abuse, might lack self-confidence, and find it tough to perform better in school. Nekesa (2009), carried out a study on the influence of child abuse on children's attendance and discipline in secondary schools in Kampala District, Uganda. The study was carried out after evidence of increased child abuse in different parts of Uganda. The design for the study was survey. The population of the study was 83 students randomly selected from 8 schools of Kampala District. The methods of data collection were questionnaire and interview and the method of data analysis was chart and percentage. The study found out that there was a strong positive correlation between child abuse and school attendance. There were many cases of children who failed to go to school because of child abuse. There were also more cases of indiscipline among children who experienced child abuse.

Obinaju (2010) conducted a study on the relationship between sexual abuse and academic performance of junior secondary school students Iseinyi, Oyo state, Ibadon. The subjects were 475 (282 males and 193 females). The subjects were JS III students who were in their final year of Junior Secondary School. They were from 12 selected secondary schools in the education zone within the area of study. When the sample was drawn, the students had sat for the Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (JSCE) at the end of their third year in school. They had also resumed Senior Secondary One (SS1) at the time of the data collection. The classes used were randomly selected. The sample of 480 students (20 students from each of 12 schools) was drawn from the educational zone. Five of the 480 students were not accounted for in the study, making the subjects to be 475. A four-point likert scale questionnaire was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). From his findings he mentions female genital mutilation as one form of child abuse. This also falls under child abuse. This also falls under child sexual abuse because it causes harm to the sexual emotion of the girl child. Wrong statistical tools were used in the previous study and a larger sample size was used compare to the present study. The former study was carried out in the western region of Nigeria while the present study will be carried out in Northwest Nigeria.

Elarousy (2017) conducted a study on physical abuse and academic achievement of students in Government secondary school Jeddah. Three research questions were raised. Non probability convenience sampling was used to select 200 participants for the study; data analyzed using IBM, SPSS software package version 20.0. Qualitative data was described using number and percentage, while quantitative was described using minimum and maximum mean and standard deviation. The study found that physical abuse has a significant effect on academic achievement of secondary school students. The finding also confirms physical abuse includes inflicting pain on the physical body of the individual. The previous study was carried out outside Nigeria, while the present is in Nigeria. The two studies varied in their geographical locations, the former was carried out in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia while the present study will be carried out in Northwest, Nigeria. Onyeonu (2013) studied relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of secondary school students in Ikwere, River state. The researcher's targeted population consisted of teachers and students in Ikwere Local Government. 40 and 80 was sampled from teachers and students respectively. The instrument used for data collection by the researcher was a 25-item questionnaire well validated was used. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation. The findings revealed that there is positive relationship between sexual abuse and academic performance of secondary school students. Based on the findings, recommendations were made on the need to affectionate and intensified campaigns for awareness creation on the menace of

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sexual abuse as they deaden the future of the child, family and society. The researcher chooses Kaduna south Senatorial District as the focal area of study because it is one of the zones that have the loudest out-cry of number of out of school children which is not in tune with national policy on education. Therefore, these variables are selected because little or no attention has been given to them by the previous researchers in the area of study. The thrust of this study therefore, is to examine the relationship between Child-abuse and academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Southern Senatorial District, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between child abuse, self-esteem and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern Kaduna senatorial district, Kaduna State. Specifically, the sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna state.
2. To determine the relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State?
2. Is there a relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.
2. There is no significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students

Methodology

Correlational survey research design was used in this study. Correlational survey establishes relationships or association between two or more variables. It establishes the direction and magnitude of relationships or association between and among variables (Uzoечи, 2015). The population of the study comprises of 3,621 JSS11 students in the Southern Kaduna Senatorial District, of Kaduna State. The sample for this study was 351 respondents drawn from 8 junior secondary schools in the study area using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size from a given population. Simple random and proportionate sampling technique were used. Two instruments were used for data collection. A structured Questionnaire named child abuse and self-esteem of students' questionnaire (CASESQ) was constructed by the researcher, and an achievement test was conducted in English Language (termed English Language Achievement Test, ELAT) to measure the student's performance. The instrument is divided into four section A and B which contained questions on the research objectives. Experts subjected the instruments to critical appraisal for face construct and content validity which gave .81 for CASESQ and .86 for (ELAT) as rated by the experts. It yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the descriptive data. Any average mean value below 3.00 is considered low while those above it were considered high. Inferential statistics of Pearson's product moment correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State?

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Table 1: Mean and standard Deviation Showing Relationship between Physical Abuse and Students' Academic Achievement and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students

SN	Relationship between Physical Abuse and Academic Achievement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remarks
1	I feel bad when others inflict pain on me	3.02	0.70	Agree
2	I feel okay when I am beaten	2.82	1.13	Agree
3	More task makes me refrain from causing injury to others	3.02	0.70	Agree
4	Home assignment makes it difficult for me to cause pain to others	2.84	1.15	Agree
5	Fear from physical injury can affect my studies	2.79	1.35	Agree
6	Being physically insulted makes me want to refrain from going to school	2.76	1.32	Agree
7	Feeling sad from experiencing physical abuse affects my grades	2.74	0.68	Agree
8	Unnecessary been beating by teachers and classmates before and during assessment affects my studies	3.03	0.71	Agree
Average mean		2.88		

Table 1 shows the views of respondents on relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. Results show that mean values of 3.02, 2.82, 3.02 and 2.84, 2.79, 2.76, 2.74 and 3.03 was obtained while standard deviation values of 0.70, 1.13, 0.70, 1.15, 1.35, 1.32, 0.68 and 0.71 was obtained. The average mean was given as 2.88. This value is above the acceptance mean value of 2.50. Hence, there is a high relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between Sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State

Table 2: Mean and standard Deviation Showing Relationship between Sexual Abuse and Students' Academic Achievement and Academic Performance of Secondary School

SN	Relationship between Sexual Abuse and Academic Achievement	Mean	Std. Dev	Remarks
9	I use to have sex with known persons	2.70	1.23	Agree
10	My parents taught me that my body is my own	2.76	0.70	Agree
11	I have never been forced to have sex	2.74	0.68	Agree
12	I have not engaged in sexual relationship	2.77	1.21	Agree
13	I feel highly uncomfortable when an elderly person make sex advances towards me	3.53	0.63	Agree
14	I have ever been forced to have sex with my siblings	2.49	1.27	Disagree
15	Illicit sexual experience hinders me to relate freely with people	2.76	0.70	Agree
16	Illicit sex makes me feel tired during class	2.76	0.70	Agree
Average mean		2.81		

Table 2 shows the views of respondents on relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. Results show that mean values of 2.70, 2.76, 2.74 and 2.77, 3.53, 2.49, 2.76 and 2.76 was obtained while standard deviation values of 1.23, 0.70, 0.68, 1.21, 0.63, 1.27, 0.70 and 0.70 was obtained. The average mean was given as 2.81. This value is above the acceptance mean value of 2.50. Hence, there is a high relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

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Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.

Significance of Relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.

Variables	N	R	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Physical abuse	351	0.67	0.001	Reject H ₀
Academic achievement	351			

$\alpha = 0.05$

From table the calculated value of Pearson's product moment statistics is given as 0.67 while the p-value (probability value) is given as 0.001. Hence, $p: 0.001 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of Pearson's product moment correlation (0.001) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies there is a significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State

Table 4: Significance of Relationship between sexual abuse and Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students.

Variables	N	R	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Physical abuse	351	0.73	0.000	Reject H ₀
Academic achievement	351			

$\alpha = 0.05$

From table 4, the calculated value of Pearson's product moment statistics is given as 0.73 while the p-value (probability value) is given as 0.000. Hence, $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of Pearson's product moment correlation (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies there is a significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from hypothesis one revealed there is a significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. This finding is similar to the findings of Elarousy (2017) which showed a significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of students in Government secondary school Jeddah. In addition, Adejobi et al (2013) posited that Physical child abuse refers to any disciplinary method that leaves a mark on the child. Physically abused school children may continue to function more poorly than the non-maltreated peers on a variety of academic and socio emotional measures. They may also have lower grades, more suspensions, and more grade repetitions, show less academic engagement, more social skill deficits and lower ego resiliency than the non-maltreated children, manifest multiple forms of academic risk and might show more externalizing and internalizing behavior problems.

The findings from hypothesis two revealed there is a significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. This finding is in agreement with those of Onyeonu (2013) which showed positive relationship between sexual abuse and academic performance of secondary school students. According to Alokun (2018), sexually abused children may function poorly than non-sexually abused peers on a variety of academic and socio emotional measures. They may also manifest multiple forms of academic risk and show more externalizing and internalizing behavior problems and may also loss interest in academic activities (Elarousy &Shaqiqi, 2017). Burnham (2019) opined that sexually abused students may suffer from lower social and emotional competence, diminished academic achievement and fear of more sexual abuse in sexually abused students, cognitive ability and memory scores as well as academic achievement may be lower than their peers, they may score lower on cognitive assessments and standardized tests of academic achievement, and might get suspended from school.

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Conclusion

Based on the findings that emerged from this study, it was concluded that each form of child abuse had independently related to physical abuse and sexual abuse as they results showed a significant relationship on students' academic achievement. Child abuse can affect all domains of development- physical abuse and sexual abuse all of which are interrelated.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend that:

1. The government and non-governmental organizations should liaise to ensure that child abuse through physical means is prohibited and discouraged. There laws prohibiting child physical abuse of children should be activated to ensure that offenders are prosecuted. This will enhance learning achievement in schools.
2. Parents and the society at large should be sensitized on the dangers of child sexual abuse. This should be done using mass media. With the help of NGO'S and members of the public, parents or guardians who are guilty should be arrested and prosecuted appropriately. This will ensure parents and guardians are responsible enough to enhance child academic achievement.

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